

Heterocyclic Systems containing Bridgehead Nitrogen Atom : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles, *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazines and *s*-Triazolo[3',4' : 2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline

JAG MOHAN*, G. S. R. ANJANEYULU and K. V. S. YAMINI
Department of Chemistry, Maharshi Dayanand University,
Rohtak-124 001

*Manuscript received 11 June 1990, revised 12 December 1990,
accepted 5 August 1991*

IN continuation of our earlier studies on the synthesis of thiazole fused heterocyclic systems, we report in this paper the synthesis of some interesting condensed heterocyclic systems derived from 3- α -naphthyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazole (1) and the biological activities associated with them.

3- α -Naphthyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazole (1) was prepared following the reported method¹. The reaction of 1 with chloroacetic acid and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline yielded 3- α -naphthyl-[5*H*]-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazin-6(7*H*)-one (3) and 3- α -naphthyl-[5*H*]-*s*-triazolo[3',4' : 2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-*b*]quinoxaline (5) respectively (Scheme 1). Treatment of 1 with benzoin in presence of potassium hydroxide yielded 3- α -naphthyl-6,7-diphenyl-[5*H*]-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazine (6). However, the reaction of 1 with aromatic acids in presence of POCl₃ yielded 3,6-diaryl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (2).

The reactions of 3-aminoquinazoline-4-thiones and 1,2-diamino-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles with carbon disulphide² have been reported in the literature. This prompted us to study the reaction of 1 with carbon disulphide which yielded in presence of pyridine, the expected product, 3- α -naphthyl-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole-6(5*H*)-thione (4).

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) RCOOH, POCl₃, (ii) CICH₂COOH, NaOAc, (iii) CS₂, pyridine, (iv) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline, NaOAc, (v) benzoin, KOH
 Scheme 1

Experimental

Tlc was run on silica gel G plates using acetone-benzene (1:3) as irrigant. Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer P-32 instrument downfield from TMS.

3- α -Naphthyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-s-triazole (1): It was prepared from α -naphthoylhydrazide according to the reported method¹ in 74% yield, m.p. 206° (EtOH) (Found: N, 22.70; S, 12.96. C₁₂H₁₀N₄S requires: N, 23.14; S, 13.22%); ν_{\max} 770, 790 (α -substituted naphthalene ring), 1525 (C-N), 1600, 1630 (C=C and C=N), 2610 (SH), 3030 (aromatic C-H), 3100 and 3300 cm⁻¹ (NH).

3- α -Naphthyl-6-aryl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole (2a): R=P-ClC₆H₄: A mixture of 1 (1.21 g, 0.005 mol), *p*-chlorobenzoic acid (0.78 g, 0.005 mol) and POCl₃ (10 ml) was refluxed on an oil-bath for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, poured into ice-cold water, and the solid thus separated was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (1 g, 55%), m.p. 250° (Found: C, 63.22; H, 3.29; N, 14.96; S, 9.12. C₁₉H₁₁N₄SCl requires: C, 62.90; H, 3.03; N, 15.45; S, 8.83%); ν_{\max} 745, 770 (α -substituted naphthalene ring), 840 (*p*-substituted phenyl), 1600 and 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N); δ (CDCl₃ and TFA) 7.20 (1H, dd, *J*_{2',3'} 7.2 Hz, *J*_{2',4'} 2.7 Hz, C-2'-H), 7.04-7.6 (5H, m, C-3'-H, C-4'-H, C-5'-H, C-6'-H and C-7'-H), 7.49 (4H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz, *p*-chlorophenyl protons), 7.62 (1H, dd, *J*_{7',8'} 7.2 Hz, *J*_{6',8'} 2.7 Hz, C-8'-H).

The other thiadiazole prepared similarly were 2b (R=*m*-ClC₆H₄) obtained from 1 and *m*-chlorobenzoic acid, (0.9 g, 50%), m.p. 192° (Found: C, 63.32; H, 2.87; N, 15.72; S, 8.48. C₁₉H₁₁N₄SCl

requires: C, 62.90; H, 3.03; N, 15.45; S, 8.83%); ν_{\max} 740, 780, 860 (α -substituted naphthalene ring and *m*-substituted phenyl ring), 1595, 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N); δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 7.24-7.92 (10H, m, C-2'-H, C-3'-H, C-4'-H, C-5'-H, C-6'-H, C-7'-H, C-8'-H and *m*-chlorophenyl protons C-4"-H, C-5"-H and C-6"-H) and 8.23 (1H, dd, C-2'-H).

3- α -Naphthyl-7H-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazin-6-(5H)-one (3): A mixture of 1 (1.21 g, 0.005 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.474 g, 0.005 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.41 g, 0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h, then cooled, poured into cold water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals, (0.8 g, 56%), m.p. 198° (Found: C, 60.01; H, 3.38; N, 20.35; S, 11.62. C₁₄H₁₀N₄SO requires: C, 59.57; H, 3.55; N, 19.86; S, 11.35%); ν_{\max} 760, 785 (α -substituted naphthalene ring), 1515 (C-N), 1600 (C=C and C=N), 1690 (C=O) and 3140 cm⁻¹ (NH).

3- α -Naphthyl-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole-6(5H)-thione (4): A solution of 1 (1.21 g, 0.005 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) was treated with CS₂ (0.5 ml) dropwise with stirring at room temperature and the mixture was heated with stirring in an oil-bath at 100° for 6 h. Pyridine was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in a small quantity of benzene, diluted with ether, charcoalised, filtered, solution concentrated and treated with hexane to give colourless crystals, (0.56 g, 39%), m.p. 192° (Found: C, 55.42; H, 2.58; N, 19.78; S, 22.67. C₁₃H₈N₄S₂ requires: C, 54.93; H, 2.82; N, 19.72; S, 22.54%); ν_{\max} 760, 790 (α -substituted naphthalene ring), 1195 (C=S), 1520 (C-N), 1620 (C=C and C=N) and 3150 cm⁻¹ (NH).

3- α -Naphthyl-5H-s-triazolo[3',4':2,3][1,3,4]thiadiazino[5,6-b]quinoxaline (5): A mixture of 1 (1.21 g, 0.005 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from aqueous ethanol as yellow flakes (0.9 g, 52%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 65.61; H, 3.25; N, 22.48, S, 8.97. C₂₀H₁₂N₆S requires: C, 65.22; H, 3.25; N, 22.83; S, 8.69%); ν_{\max} 760, 775, 790 (α -substituted naphthalene ring and *o*-disubstituted benzene ring), 1535 (C-N), 1610 (C=C and C=N), 3030 (aromatic CH) and 3215 cm⁻¹ (NH).

3- α -Naphthyl-6,7-diphenyl-5H-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazine (6): A mixture of 1 (1.21 g, 0.005 mol) and benzoin (1.06 g, 0.005 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was heated to get a clear solution and to the hot solution was added 2*N* KOH solution (0.5 ml). The mixture was refluxed with constant stirring for 2 h, then concentrated and allowed to cool to the room temperature. The resulting light yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as light yellow needles, (0.6 g, 30%), m.p. 238° (Found: C, 74.41; H, 4.44; N, 13.69; S, 7.85. C₂₆H₁₈N₄S requires: C, 74.64; H, 4.31; N, 13.40; S, 7.66%); ν_{\max} 680, 720, 750, 770, 810

(monosubstituted benzene and α -substituted naphthalene ring), 1 580, 1 640 (C=C and C=N) and 3 360 cm^{-1} (NH); δ ($\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{TFA}$) 7.18 (1H, bs, exchangeable with D_2O); 7.47 (1H, dd, C-2'-H, $J_{2',3'}$ 7.2 Hz, $J_{2',4'}$ 2.7 Hz, NH), 7.80–8.80 (4H, m, C-3'-H, C-4'-H, C-6'-H, C-7'-H), 8.40 (1H, dd (degenerate), C-5'-H), 8.68 (10H, phenyl protons) and 8.94 (1H, dd, $J_{7',8'}$ 7.2 Hz, $J_{6',8'}$ 2.7 Hz C-8'-H).

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds 2, 3, 5 and 6 were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and the fungus *Candida albicans* by neat samples and serial plate dilution method³.

MIC values of 2 ($\text{R} = p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$) against *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans* were found to be 125 and 250 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and that of 3 500 and 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively. MIC values of 5 and 6 were $>1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and showed activity against *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*, when tested as neat samples and thus may be used for local application subject to toxicity studies.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. D. R. Arora, Department of Microbiology, Medical College, Rohtak, for biological screening, to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (G.S.R.A.) and to Head of the Chemistry Department, Maharshi Dayanand University, for facilities.

References

1. J. R. REID and N. D. HEINDEL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 925.
2. P. B. TALUKDAR, S. K. SENGUPTA and A. K. DATTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, **15**, 1110.
3. H. NAKAHARA, T. ISHIKAWA, Y. SARAI, T. KONDO and S. MITSUHASHI, *Nature*, 1977, **266**, 165.